

EXAMINING THE RELATIONSHIP OF CONSUMER'S PURCHASE BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING BEHAVIOUR DURING COVID-19 IN SELANGOR, MALAYSIA

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ABSTRACT

The global pandemic (COVID-19) issue has had an impact on many facets of our daily existence, from the way we go about performing particular tasks to the extent of how we think. This paper emphasises how consumer preferences, buying habits, and shopping behaviour have all been impacted. Due to the movement control order (MCO) and standard operating procedures (SOP), many shops are forced to abruptly close their locations without knowing when they can resume their regular operations. Numerous retailers have also been compelled by this circumstance to switch from their conventional offline purchase methods to online platforms. The goal of this study is to comprehend consumers' online shopping behaviour in Selangor, Malaysia, during COVID-19. The theoretical framework is developed using the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) paradigm. Consumer attitude, perception of behaviour control, and subjective norm were examined as the three primary variables of consumer behaviour based on (TPB). The survey method was used to collect data from consumers, and correlation analysis was used to analyse the data. 435 responses to self-administered structured questionnaires were gathered for the data analysis. The results of this study demonstrate a significant, and strong association between consumers' online shopping behaviour during COVID-19. This information will help all retailers throughout the pandemic better understand consumer behaviour and enable them to continue operating their businesses despite the rapid change. Retailers would also have a better understanding of the features that customers look for in an online purchasing method, such as a user-friendly website, secure online payment methods, and easy navigation pages.

Keywords: COVID-19, consumer behaviour, attitude, subjective norms, perceived behaviour control, online shopping purchase behaviour

INTRODUCTION

The pandemic caused by the COVID-19 virus has had a significant effect on both the health of people all over the world and the economy of the entire world. According to Turner (2020), the pandemic has been more devastating to the world's economy than any other natural disaster that occurred during these 30 years, including the economic damage that occurred between 2008 and 2009 (Tuncer, 2020). It was without a doubt the most significant event that took place

during the preceding year (2020). During a pandemic of influenza, there will almost certainly be shifts in both the general public's opinion and overall behaviour (Xu & Peng, 2019). Previous research on the behaviour of consumers during an emergency has primarily focused on the topic in the context of economic recessions or financial crises (Tuncer, 2020). The public is compelled to adopt and socially distance themselves when confronted with a serious threat, such as a pandemic that causes serious illness or death (S, M.D., Lane, & Redfield, 2020). Many countries are experiencing lockdowns, in which businesses are forced to close because of restrictions. Nonetheless, online shopping and consumer research are becoming increasingly important parts of daily life (Hao Chang & Meyerhoefer, 2020). In order to put this theory into practice, one must have a grasp of consumer behaviour and shopping behaviours in a setting where residents are urged to remain inside their houses until absolutely necessary. Determining what influences consumer behaviour during this pandemic and how this will affect online shopping is of the utmost significance. Depending on changes in consumer behaviour, retailers will also have a better grasp of how to effectively market those products to customers, whether through the use of online retailing or by promoting more conventional purchasing methods.

The primary objective of this study is to fill a research gap by determining whether the consequences of behavioural changes associated with online shopping in Selangor would persist after COVID-19 and whether or not the pandemic has had any impact at all. The growing trend of online shopping has had the most significant effect on consumer behaviour during the pandemic; the study focuses on the viewpoint of an online consumer. Using the TBP theory, this study will investigate the consumer's intention for future online purchases by analysing the effects the pandemic has had on the consumer's already established patterns of behaviour as an online shopper on the internet.

Research Questions

The following are the research questions:

1. Is there a relationship between consumer attitudes and their online shopping behaviours during COVID-19 in Selangor, Malaysia?
2. Is there a relationship between consumers' subjective norms and their online shopping behaviours during COVID-19 in Selangor, Malaysia?
3. Is there a relationship between consumers' perceived behavioural control and their online shopping behaviours during COVID-19 in Selangor, Malaysia?

Research Objectives

The objectives of this study are as stated below:

1. To examine the relationship between consumers' attitudes towards online shopping behaviours during COVID-19 in Selangor, Malaysia
2. To examine the relationship between consumers' subjective norms and online shopping behaviours during COVID-19 in Selangor, Malaysia
3. To examine the relationship between consumers' perceived behavioural control and online shopping behaviours during COVID-19 in Selangor, Malaysia

The behaviour of Malaysian consumers has a significant impact on the demand for online shopping activities. Consumer purchasing behaviour has been influenced by the lockdowns in the countries, as there would be a lack of items and services available in various outlets and retailers. As a result, consumers should rely heavily on online shopping platforms to meet their basic survival needs (Müller, 2022). Figure 1 shows a recent survey done by Rakuten in 2021, There are many reasons why consumers are looking into online shopping during COVID-19. According to a survey performed by Rakuten Insight in Malaysia, 62 percent of respondents claimed that they increased their online purchases because their family was adopting social distancing and wanted to spend less time outside the home. This study also reported that Malaysians made more online purchases throughout the Covid-19 pandemic.

Figure 1. Reasons for Increasing Online Shopping Purchases
Source: Rakuten Survey 2021

Conceptual Framework

Independent Variables

Dependent Variable

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework adapted from Ajzen (1991) Theory of Planned Behaviour

Research Hypotheses

The research hypotheses developed for this study are as follows:

H1: There is a significant relationship between consumer attitudes and their online shopping behaviours during COVID-19 in Selangor, Malaysia.

H2: There is a significant relationship between consumers' subjective norms and their online shopping behaviours during COVID-19 in Selangor, Malaysia.

H3: There is a significant relationship between consumers' perceived behavioural control and their online shopping behaviours during COVID-19 in Selangor, Malaysia.

Consumer Attitudes Toward Online Shopping Behaviour During COVID-19

Since the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic (early 2020), consumers have started stockpiling, which is a significant change from their usual purchase behaviour. Due to consumers' increasing health concerns and the shops' limited accessibility, there has been an immediate increase in demand for alternative distribution methods. The chosen purchasing channel of consumers is significantly impacted by unexpected rules that cause social division. While the number of people buying groceries online has increased gradually over the past ten years (Harris, Riley, Riley, & Hand, 2017), this growth has substantially increased during the COVID-19 pandemic (Pantano & Pizzi, 2020). Aside from that, older and less tech-savvy consumers have started to discover and enjoy online shopping, embracing the security that it offers.

Consumers' Subjective Norms Toward Online Shopping Behaviour during COVID-19

According to Ajzen's (1991) Theory of Planned Behaviour, subjective norms are the perceived pressure exerted by others, such as neighbours, friends, peers, and those who engage in the behaviour of interest, and they can have a direct or indirect impact on the respondent's behaviour. Subjective norms are beliefs about what the majority of important customers think about whether or not a person should engage in problematic behaviour.

A person's impression of a particular behaviour displayed by a group is referred to as their "subjective norms" in the Theory of Planned Behaviour. This perception, therefore, affects the individual's willingness to cooperate with the behaviour being displayed by others as well as the degree to which the individual wishes to comply with the individuals or groups showing the behaviour in issue (Ajzen, 1991). Subjective norms contain two different categories of descriptive norms: the first is the pressure an individual feels to comply with the norms, and the second is the individual's personal experience and opinion on the prevalence of this behaviour or whether or not others would adopt it. These two descriptive norms are examples of subjective norms (Ajzen, 1991). The process of influencing other people's behaviour involves this interdependence between individuals, which has an impact on it.

Perceived Behavioural Control of Consumers Toward Online Shopping Behaviour During COVID-19

In the theory of planned behaviour, the intention to perform a behaviour is based on attitudes and subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control is a key component. The term "perceived behavioural control" refers to an individual's sense of how easy or difficult it is to engage in the behaviour of interest, and it fluctuates depending on circumstances and behaviour (Ajzen, 1991). The findings of various studies show that risk perception affects both consumer behaviour and people's behaviour in their daily lives (Long & Khoi, 2020). Depending on the situation, "degrees of cost, reward, level of damage, and level of risk appetite" have an impact on consumers' choice-making. A previous study (Long & Khoi, 2020) found that how people feel about risk is a key factor that affects both their intentions and their buying decisions.

METHODOLOGY

The quantitative approach method was applied in this study. Primary data is information collected by the researchers through questionnaires, interviews, and studies with the explicit purpose of assisting the researchers in comprehending the topic of the research. Data from previous studies, government organizations, and other sources is referred to as "secondary data." To gather primary data for this study, questionnaires were used in a survey that was sent out to Selangor citizens. The convenience sampling method was applied to a problem's initial investigation. This survey covered 435 residences in total and was distributed using Survey Monkey to the residences via WhatsApp and emails. The Likert scale and multiple choice are the two methods employed in the questionnaire's construction. Multiple-choice questions were used in the early sections of the questionnaire. In the second phase, the Likert scale is used to gather information about nominal values, which are largely used to measure the variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 displays the demographic profile of the respondents. There are slightly more male respondents (53%) than female respondents. About 23% are between 25- 35 years old, 120 (28%) are between 36- 45 years old, and 21% are between the ages of 46 -55, There are 75(17%) aged 56-65, and 50(11%) are in the older age category (66-75). Of the 345 respondents, 29% were Indian, 28% were Malay, 24% were Chinese, and 19% were from other ethnicities.

The preferred online shopping platform is Lazada (31%) and Shopee (29%) followed by Zalora (23%), The respondents usually shop monthly (46%) or weekly (45%) and 8.9% do online shopping daily. The top ten most popular products bought by people are as follows: books (23%), groceries (21%), food (21%), apparel (20%), accessories (20%), home and furniture (17%), technology (9.2%), other (4.6%), and flowers (2.3%).

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Respondents

Variables	Category	Frequency n, (N=435)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	232	53
	Female	203	47
	Total	435	100.0
Age Group	25 - 35	100	23
	36 - 45	120	28
	46 - 55	90	21
	56 - 65	75	17
	66 - 75	50	11
	Total	435	100
Ethnic Origin	Malay	123	28
	Chinese	105	24
	Indian	125	29
	Other	82	19
	Total	435	100
Preferred Online Platform	ZALORA	100	23
	Shopee	126	29
	LAZADA	134	31
	Other	75	17
	Total	435	100
How Often do you Shop online	Daily	39	8.9
	Weekly	196	45
	Monthly	200	46
	When it required	0	0
	Total	435	100
Product Purchased	Fashion, Clothing and accessories	89	20
	Health and beauty	70	16

Books	40	23
Groceries, food and drinks	91	21
Technology	40	9.2
Home and furniture	75	17
Flowers and gifts	10	2.3
Others	20	4.6
Total	435	100

Reliability Test

The reliability test was performed, and the results for the independent variables and dependent variables are provided in Table 2 below. The reliability test was used to verify that the obtained results were reliable and devoid of any sporadic errors (Livinston, 2018). The reliability analysis results are shown in Table 2 below as an interpretation of Cronbach's alpha (α) for Reliability Analysis (Hair, Tomas, & Ringle, 2017). Cronbach's alpha for consumers' attitudes was 0.664, while consumers' subjective norms were = 0.803 and consumers' perceived behaviour control was 0.976. In terms of dependent variables, purchase behaviour during COVID-19 was 0.992.

Table 2. Reliability analysis results (n=435)

Variable	n	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
Independent variable			
Attitude	435	0.664	6
Subjective Norms	435	0.803	6
Perceived Behavioural Control	435	0.976	6
Dependent Variable			
Purchase Behaviour During COVID-19	435	0.992	12

Table 3. Frequency analysis for Attitude (n=435)

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
I prefer doing both online and offline shopping before COVID19.	25(6%)	37(9%)	52(12%)	128(29%)	193(44%)
I either do my product information search online or walk-in to a physical store before COVID-19?	84(19%)	84(19%)	67(15%)	79(18%)	121(28%)
I find it convenient to buy any products anytime using shopping online.	47(11%)	20(5%)	30(7%)	51(12%)	287(66%)
I find it convenient to buy any products anytime using shopping online.	25(6%)	40(9%)	36(8%)	74(17%)	260(60%)
I get on time delivery by doing online shopping.	50(11%)	40(9%)	100(23%)	60(14%)	185(43%)
I feel online shopping saves my travelling time.	30(7%)	21(5%)	30(7%)	97(22%)	257

Consumers are happy and satisfied when they shop online since it saves them time and is handy. They also enjoy doing online purchasing even before COVID-19. Based on the survey results in Table 3, 287(66%) respondents strongly think that it is convenient to buy any products using online shopping.

Based on the survey results in Table 4, 258(59%) respondents strongly agree that they prefer to shop online on trustworthy websites, and 250(57%) strongly agree that they prefer to buy from websites that provide quality information and product reviews.

Table 4. Frequency analysis for Subjective Norms (n=435)

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
I feel that purchasing online contain more risks, than purchasing in retail stores.	190(44%)	150(34%)	45(10%)	30(7%)	20(5%)
I do not feel comfortable sharing my financial details on an online shop.	30(7%)	80(18%)	50(11%)	132(30%)	143(33%)
I feel comfortable sharing my financial details on an online shop.	46(11%)	40(9%)	80(18%)	124(29%)	145(33%)
I found that online shopping is not user friendly	200(46%)	120(28%)	50(11%)	40(9%)	25(6%)
I prefer buying from websites that provides me with quality information and product review.	35(8%)	20(5%)	30(7%)	100(23%)	250(57%)
I prefer to shop online from a trustworthy website (popular websites).	38(9%)	40(9%)	10(2%)	89(20%)	258(59%)

Based on the survey results in Table 5 for perceived behavioural control, only 53 (12%) respondents strongly agree that they have had a bad experience while shopping online and only 69 (16%) strongly agree that they were not satisfied with the item they received. Meanwhile, only 30(7%) experienced a long wait to receive the item. About, 260(60%) strongly agree that they prefer websites with easy navigation for their online shopping and 150(34%) strongly believe that familiarity with the website before making any purchase reduces the risk of shopping online.

Table 5. Frequency analysis for Perceived Behavioural Control (n=435)

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
I had a bad experience in online shopping all the time.	113(26%)	100(23%)	96(22%)	73(17%)	53(12%)
I was not satisfied with item that I received in online shopping.	105(24%)	122(28%)	50(11%)	89(20%)	69(16%)
I experience a long wait time to receive my item.	111(26%)	117(27%)	150(34%)	27(6%)	30(7%)
I experience bad after-sales support in online shopping.	98(23%)	112(26%)	105(24%)	89(20%)	31(7%)
I believe that familiarity with the website before making actual purchase reduce the risk of shopping online.	60(14%)	70(16%)	66(15%)	89(20%)	150(34%)
I choose websites with easy navigation and user-friendly layouts to do my online shopping.	35(8%)	20(5%)	40(9%)	80(18%)	260(60%)

The survey results in Table 6 show that during COVID-19, 220 (51%) strongly agree that they do online shopping more frequently due to Covid-19 and 189 (43%) do online shopping to ensure the safety of their families. About 268(62%) strongly agree that online shopping was more convenient, and 220 (51%) said they did more online shopping during COVID-19.

Table 6. Frequency analysis for Online Shopping Behaviour during COVID-19

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
I started to do online shopping more frequently for all my daily items and other necessities due to COVID-19.	41(9%)	43(10%)	30(7%)	101(23%)	220(51%)
I started to do online shopping due to Movement Control Order (MCO).	23 (5%)	26(6%)	40(9%)	167(38%)	179(41%)
I started to search online more for all product information online after COVID-19?	67(15%)	68(16%)	80(18%)	100(23%)	120(28%)
I started to do more online shopping and product comparison online due to COVID-19.	35(8%)	67(15%)	99(23%)	110(25%)	124(29%)
I started to do online shopping to ensure the safeness of my family during COVID-19	26(6%)	40(9%)	30(7%)	150(34%)	189(43%)
I started to shop online from a trustworthy website during COVID-19.	20(5%)	30(7%)	50(11%)	168(39%)	167(38%)
I'm confident and feel safe while shopping online during COVID-19.	21(5%)	87(20%)	54(12%)	124(29%)	149(34%)
I found that most online shopping becoming more user friendly during COVID-19.	20(5%)	87(20%)	50(11%)	100(23%)	178(41%)
I had a good experience in online shopping, I will do more online shopping even its not during COVID-19 period.	20(5%)	90(21%)	60(14%)	120(28%)	145(33%)
Shopping online is more time efficient, than retail shopping during COVID-19.	60(14%)	70(16%)	66(15%)	89(20%)	150(34%)
Online shopping is more convenient during COVID-19, because I can take my time to compare products and price without time concerns.	38(9%)	40(9%)	10(2%)	89(20%)	258(59%)
It is more convenient to shop online without having to go outside during COVID-19.	25(6%)	40(9%)	36(8%)	74(17%)	260(60%)

Correlation Analysis

Correlation Analysis was conducted to test the following hypotheses. The results are shown in Table 7.

H1: There is a significant relationship between consumer attitudes and their online shopping behaviours during COVID-19 in Selangor, Malaysia.

Correlation analysis results show that there was a significant moderate positive relationship ($r = 0.465$, $p < 0.05$), between consumers' attitudes and their online shopping behaviour during COVID-19 in Selangor, Malaysia as shown in Table 7. As a result, this hypothesis 1 is supported.

H2: There is a significant relationship between consumers' subjective norms and their online shopping behaviours during COVID-19 in Selangor, Malaysia.

There also exists a significant moderate positive relationship ($r = 0.416$, $p < 0.05$) between consumers' subjective norms and their online shopping behaviours during COVID-19 in Selangor, Malaysia. As a result, this hypothesis 2 is supported.

H3: There is a significant relationship between consumers' perceived behavioural control and their online shopping behaviours during COVID-19 in Selangor, Malaysia.

However, there exists a significant and strong positive relationship ($r = 0.957$, $p < 0.05$) between consumers' perceived behaviour control and their online shopping behaviours during COVID-19. As a result, this hypothesis 3 is strongly supported.

Table 7. Summary of Pearson Correlation results

Hypothesis	Pearson Correlation(r)	p-Value	Findings
H1: There is a significant relationship between consumer attitudes and their online shopping behaviours during COVID-19 in Selangor, Malaysia.	0.465	<0.000	significant and moderate positive relationship
H2: There is a significant relationship between consumers' subjective norms and their online shopping behaviours during COVID-19 in Selangor, Malaysia.	0.416	<0.000	significant and moderate positive relationship
H3: There is a significant relationship between consumers' perceived behavioural control and their online shopping behaviours during COVID-19 in Selangor, Malaysia.	0.957	<0.000	significant and very strong positive relationship

CONCLUSION

Consumers are comfortable with online shopping due to the convenience of doorstep delivery services from any part of the world, which has changed many retailers' marketing techniques in recent decades (Bucko et al., 2018). With the emergence of COVID-19, consumer behaviour has changed drastically, forcing businesses to move away from their most devoted brick-and-mortar (offline shopping) customers to online shoppers. This huge change is very unusual, and it has forced businesses to develop unique solutions to adapt to the new normal (Carnevale & Hatak, 2020). Consumer behaviour has changed drastically around the world because of movement restrictions and social distancing orders (Jagdish, 2020). As a result, numerous types of enterprises have been forced to re-evaluate their marketing strategies and discover new ways to attract homebound clients.

This study in Selangor, Malaysia, investigates how consumers' behaviour towards online shopping changed during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study used the original TPB model as the underlying theory to investigate consumer online behaviour in Selangor's growing economy, and it found that attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control have a positive and significant impact on consumers' behaviour towards online shopping. All three research hypotheses have been supported. The findings show that retailers should understand consumer behaviour to sustain their online businesses now and in the future.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

All authors are participants in the data collection, analysis, writing and revising the manuscript.

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